

"INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE" AND ITS MAIN TASKS

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Abstract. *In this article, "intangible cultural heritage" and its goals and tasks, the concept of intangible cultural heritage and its essence, issues of intangible cultural heritage in socio-cultural activities.*

Key words: *Intangible cultural heritage, folk art, UNESCO, living traditions, Socio-cultural activities, protection of traditional culture and folklore, dance, music, artifacts.*

«НЕМАТЕРИАЛЬНОЕ КУЛЬТУРНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ» И ЕГО ОСНОВНЫЕ ЗАДАЧИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье «нематериальное культурное наследие» и его цели и задачи, понятие нематериального культурного наследия и его сущность, вопросы нематериального культурного наследия в социально-культурной деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *Нематериальное культурное наследие, народное творчество, ЮНЕСКО, живые традиции, социально-культурная деятельность, охрана традиционной культуры и фольклора, танец, музыка, артефакты.*

The concept of intangible cultural heritage - traditions, folk art (speech, dance, music, performing arts), forms of expression of identity, knowledge and reflect skills as well as associated equipment, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces.

The purpose of the science of intangible cultural heritage is to form in the minds of young people the traditions of the Uzbek people, which have gained special importance and reached the level of value, as well as knowledge and skills related to them.

The following are the main tasks of the science of intangible cultural heritage:

- Formation of knowledge and skills in the types and forms of intangible cultural heritage at the level of demand of socio-cultural activity students;
- To acquire sufficient skills in this regard in students based on examples of folklore;
- To ensure that people have a sufficient idea of performing arts and games;
- To further strengthen students' knowledge of traditions that have a special cultural value;
- Teaching the normative legal framework and administrative management system aimed at preservation, protection and transmission of intangible cultural heritage to the next generation.

- Teaching the wide use of cultural tourism programs in the promotion of intangible cultural heritage.

Not long ago, the expressions "social and cultural activity" and "intangible cultural heritage" came into use. The expression "social-cultural activity" was used to replace the expression "cultural-educational work", which was very widely used in its time, and the expression "cultural-educational work" another phrase - "cultural-educational works" is also used.

Today, these new expressions are used not as opposites, but as complementary expressions, and it has become natural for them to mean separate meanings in various educational, scientific literature and contemporary press lines.

Since the phrase "intangible cultural heritage" is being used relatively late, it is a bit more difficult for many to understand, so we will dwell a little on the history of this phrase entering the world lexicon.

The adoption of the Convention on "Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage" by UNESCO on October 17, 2003, and the Convention on "Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions" on October 20, 2005 completed the process of entering full-fledged consumption.

In fact, issues of intangible cultural heritage and its protection began with UNESCO's 1989 Recommendations on "Protection of Traditional Culture and Folklore". Since 1994, the "Living (Living) Masterpieces of Humanity" Program has been launched in order to organize the official recognition of those who preserve and transmit the intangible cultural heritage by national systems (states) and support for the transmission of this heritage to the next generation.

In 1997-1998, UNESCO approved the Program "Proclamation of the Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity", which made it possible to compile and announce the list of intangible cultural heritage preserved by the nations of the world. We know well that "Boysun cultural environment" was included in this list in 2001 and "Shashmaqom" in 2003.

In the 90s of the last century, on the basis of experts' conclusions, it was determined that drastic and strict measures should be taken to protect the existing intangible cultural heritage, and the work in this direction was accelerated. As a result, at the 31st session of the UNESCO General Conference held in 2001, it was planned to create a Convention that would serve as a new international regulatory mechanism. Thus, at the 32nd session of the General Conference of UNESCO on October 17, 2003, the Convention "Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage" was adopted.

This Convention provides the following definitions of "intangible cultural heritage", its areas of manifestation and protection.

The concept of "intangible cultural heritage" reflects traditions, forms of expression of identity, knowledge and skills, as well as related equipment, objects, artifacts and cultural spaces, which in turn are communities, groups, and in special cases it means that a specific person is recognized as a part of his cultural heritage. Such intangible cultural heritage, which is passed down from generation to generation, is always created by certain communities and groups depending on their environment, nature and their history, and it forms their identity, a sense of inheritance, and thus human creativity. and promote respect for cultural diversity.

Intangible cultural heritage is manifested in the following areas:

- a) oral traditions and forms of self-expression, including language as a factor reflecting intangible cultural heritage;
- b) in performing arts;
- c) customs, ceremonies, holidays of society;
- g) a collection of knowledge and customs related to nature and the universe;
- d) knowledge and skills related to traditional crafts.

The word "preservation" means to ensure the vitality of intangible cultural heritage, at the same time, to identify, document, research, preserve, protect, popularize, increase its role, and promote it, mainly with the help of formal and informal education. means enhancing and re-establishing various aspects of such heritage.

The process of ratification of this Convention in Uzbekistan began in 2005. As a result of the comprehensive study of the Convention, appropriate proposals were prepared and submitted to the Oliy Majlis through the Cabinet of Ministers, and as a result, the Convention "Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage" was ratified in December 2007. According to international standards, the Republic of Uzbekistan became a state party to this Convention six months after the submission of the ratification documents, that is, from April 29, 2008.

Based on the rules of acceptance of international documents, it was necessary to revise the issues related to the intangible cultural heritage in the existing legislation in Uzbekistan and, if necessary, make appropriate changes and additions. In this regard, a working group was formed under the leadership of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of Uzbekistan, which was adopted in 2001 to introduce amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects". Proposals have been prepared. These proposals were studied in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, and finally on October 9, 2009, the Law of the

Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments to the Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects" was adopted. Law No. RQ-228 was adopted.

In addition to the process of revising the national legislation based on international norms, the process of studying the intangible cultural heritage, organizing its protection and passing it on to the next generation was organized. In particular, during the months of February-March 2008, the issue of implementation of the provisions of the Convention "Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage" in the Ministry of Culture and Sports and local councils of people's deputies was studied.

Based on the information studied by the special commission, on April 30, 2008, this issue was discussed at a special meeting attended by representatives of the upper and lower chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and a corresponding decision was made. As one of the most important tasks in this decision, the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was entrusted with the task of developing a project of the State Program for the Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage in cooperation with interested ministries and agencies. In February 2010, a special Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of the State program dedicated to the protection of intangible cultural heritage was announced, and in June 2010, the draft of this State program was submitted to the Cabinet of Ministers. On October 7, 2010, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 222 "On the approval of the State program for the protection, preservation, promotion and use of intangible cultural heritage objects in 2010-2020" was adopted.

Tasks in the state program are summarized in the 8 areas shown below.

1. Improving the legal framework and administrative management system aimed at preservation, protection and transmission of intangible cultural heritage to the next generation.
2. Registration of intangible cultural heritage and documentation of information about them.
3. Organization of training and professional development of industry specialists.
4. Practical measures of conservation of intangible cultural heritage objects.
5. Propaganda and campaigning activities on preservation of intangible cultural heritage and organization of its protection.
6. Development of a network of cooperation in the protection of intangible cultural heritage.
7. Wide use of cultural tourism programs in promotion of intangible cultural heritage.
8. Further improvement of the financing system for preservation of intangible cultural heritage.

The state program consists of a total of 57 items and it shows the main directions of protection, preservation, promotion and use of our intangible cultural heritage for the next 10 years.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the protection of intangible cultural heritage is reflected in our national legislation. Organizations and institutions specializing in this field and their specialists are responsible for the gradual implementation of the tasks reflected in the International Convention and our national legislation.

Although the phrase "intangible cultural heritage", as we mentioned above, has come into use in recent days, it is important to preserve our national heritage, which we have traditionally expressed with the expressions and words of "folk art", "folklore", and to pass it on to the next generation, from the first days of our independence, great attention was paid to the issues of its effective use in youth education.

Initially, folklore-ethnographic groups operating in the regions and performers of ancient musical instruments were involved in events dedicated to Navruz and Independence national holidays held in Tashkent, and the work that started with them being given a place on the biggest stage of our country was continued consistently. Issues of studying folk art, developing amateur art were introduced to all stages of education starting from preschool educational institutions.

As a result of this, amateur folklore groups were formed not only in every district and city of our country, but also in almost all educational institutions: Nowadays, higher education and secondary special, vocational education and general education. This is evidenced by the traditional organization of "Treasure", "Heritage", "Living Traditions" competitions in secondary educational institutions.

In connection with the adoption of the International Convention on the Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage, objects of intangible cultural heritage included in the "List of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity" ("Boysun Cultural Environment" included from Uzbekistan and jointly included with Tajikistan "Shashmaqom") were transferred to the new "Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage". In this list, the "Katta Ashula" candidate recommended from Uzbekistan in 2009 and the "Navroz" candidates recommended together with 7 other countries were included. Thus, at present, there are 4 intangible cultural heritages related to Uzbekistan in the Representative list, and such an indicator is not observed in any country of the former union. Currently, it is planned to create 4 separate lists of intangible cultural heritage in our country.

These are:

1. List of intangible cultural heritage objects that should be immediately protected.
2. List of candidates recommended for inclusion in the representative list of world intangible cultural heritage.

3. National list of intangible cultural heritage.

4. Consists of local lists of intangible cultural heritage. All the above-mentioned lists must be constantly updated and supplemented. In particular, it will be removed from this list after the danger in the object on the list, which requires immediate protection measures, has been eliminated. Or, if an object included in the local list is recommended to be included in the National Register according to the results of the historical and cultural expertise, it will be removed from the previous list and transferred to another, etc.

Taking into account the important role of socio-cultural activity in the formation of the spirituality of society members, it can be clearly seen from the above examples that it is directly related to the intangible cultural heritage. After all, as stated in the work of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "High spirituality - an invincible power", in the process of globalization, we will have to fight with our national intangible cultural heritage against the invading "mass culture" from the West. In this case, the State program approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 222 "On approval of the State program for the protection, preservation, promotion and use of intangible cultural heritage objects in 2010-2020" serves as a valid program. can do.

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